

Applying Action Research to Micro-frontends Migration

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Motivation

Accelerating application development typically involves expanding the developer and team count

This, in turn, leads to an uptick in parallel work on shared codebases, possibly resulting in an increasing frequency of conflicting commits

Objective

Assess whether a micro-frontends architecture enables multiple development teams to concurrently collaborate on the same application while minimizing the impact of conflicting commits to the code base

Apply the architecture to a real project using an action research methodology, and analyze the resulting impact on the development process

Micro-frontends

The image features a solid blue background with three light blue, curved, arrow-like shapes pointing from the bottom-left towards the top-right. The text "Micro-frontends" is centered in a white, sans-serif font.

Micro-frontends

"An architectural style where independently deliverable frontend applications are composed into a greater whole"

Cam Jackson - <https://martinfowler.com/articles/micro-frontends.html>
(2019)

Monolithic

Micro Frontends

Benefits

B1 - Support for different technologies

B2 - Autonomous cross-functional teams

B3 - Independent development, deployment and managing and running

B4 - Better testability

B5 - Improved fault isolation, resiliation

B6 - Highly Scalable

B7 - Faster Onboarding

B8 - Fast initial load

B9 - Improved performance

B10 - Future proof

Bonus - Reusability

Peltonen, S., Mezzalira, L., and Taibi, D. - **Motivations, benefits, and issues for adopting micro-frontends: A multivocal literature review.** (2021)

Issues

I1 - Increased payload size

I2 - Code Duplication

I3 - Shared Dependencies

I4 - UX consistency

I5 - Monitoring

I6 - Increased level of complexity

I7 - Governance

I8 - Islands of knowledge

I9 - Environment differences

I10 - Higher risk when releasing updates

I11 - Accessibility challenges

Peltonen, S., Mezzalana, L., and Taibi, D. - **Motivations, benefits, and issues for adopting micro-frontends: A multivocal literature review.** (2021)

Principles

1 - Split

Horizontal or Vertical

2 - Composition

Server-side, Edge-side or Client-side

3 - Routing

Shell, Lambda@Edge or during Server-side composition

4 - Communication

Web storage, Cookies, Query String and Event Emitter

Taibi, D., and Mezzalana, L., - **Micro-frontends: Principles, implementations, and pitfalls.** (2022)

Split: Vertical

Team A

Team B

VERTICAL SPLIT

Split: Horizontal

HORIZONTAL SPLIT

Composition

Routing

Communication: Between Views

Communication: Horizontal Split

Application Changes

Horizontal Split

- Project update component present in both views
- Intention to reuse micro-frontends in other applications

File Edit View Window Help

project-selection-microfrontend

Jupiter
Interpretação sísmica objetivando identificação dos horizontes e o reconhecimento das principais facies.
28/08/2020 15:00

Caratinga
Descrição sucinta do projeto de facies.
23/06/2020 16:01

Bacia de [REDACTED]
Descrição não sucinta do projeto. Interpretação sísmica objetivando identificação dos horizontes e o reconhecimento das...
03/04/2020 17:34

Roncador
Descrição sucinta do projeto de facies.
20/01/2020 06:00

Iracema
Descrição sucinta do projeto de facies.
31/12/2019

Rio Grande
Interpretação sísmica objetivando identificação dos horizontes e o reconhecimento das principais facies.
07/04/2019

DADOS DE ENTRADA DO PROJETO | Jupiter

project-info-microfrontend

GERAL DADOS GEOMETRIA

Nome: *
Jupiter

Id do projeto: [REDACTED] *
[REDACTED] Interpretação sísmica objetivando identificação dos horizontes e o reconhecimento das principais facies.

Descrição:
Interpretação sísmica objetivando identificação dos horizontes e o reconhecimento das principais facies.

File Edit View Window Help

FLUXO DO PROJETO | Projeto [redacted] | Jupiter | Projeto [redacted]

pipeline-microfrontend

Jupiter

- Padrão
- Ativo
- Satisfatório

PARÂMETROS [redacted] 04/09/2023 14:20

phase-parametrization-microfrontend

Máquina local: [redacted]

Última execução: 23/12/2020 05:00

ENTRADAS SAÍDAS

Identificação (ID): *

[redacted]_1022

Identificação (ID) de [redacted]

[redacted]_2024

Identificação (ID) de [redacted]

[redacted]_1020

[redacted]

[redacted]

[redacted]

[redacted]

[redacted]

4,8,16,32,64

[redacted]

[redacted]

512

EXECUÇÃO

Diretório local de resultados: * ⓘ

/u/xpto/[redacted]_jupiter/

Diretório remoto:

TABELA DE EXECUÇÕES | KMEANS_1022

execution-table-microfrontend

Estado	Identificador	Submissão	Máquina
Perdido	admin@FLOW.WAAXaPYJ7s	23/12/2020 05:00	[redacted]
Perdido	admin@FLOW.WAAXaPYJ7s	22/12/2020 05:00	[redacted]
Falha na inicialização	admin@FLOW.WAAXaPYJ7s	21/12/2020 05:00	[redacted]
Erro	admin@FLOW.WAAXaPYJ7s	20/12/2020 05:00	[redacted]

Client-side Composition

Route Definition


```
{  
  path: 'project-selection',  
  loadChildren: () =>  
    loadRemoteModule({  
      remoteEntry: `${environment.projectSelectionUrl}/remoteEntry.js`,  
      remoteName: 'projectSelection',  
      exposedModule: './Module',  
    }).then((m) => m.ProjectSelectionModule),  
},
```

Communication Services

Feature Service Example

ProjectFeatureService
allProjects: Project[] allProjects\$: Observable<Project[]> selectedProject: Project selectedProject\$: Observable<Project>
loadProjects(): void createProject(project: Project): void deleteProject(id: string): void updateProject(changes: ObjectPatch[]): void selectProject(id: string): void

Communication Services

Feature Service Method Example

Repositories

Common Libraries

- Microfrontends UI
- Microfrontends Core
 - Environment Service
 - Authorization Service
 - AppStateFeature Service
 - WebSocketConnector Service
- Flow-in-memory-db

Repositories

Feature Libraries

- Microfrontends File Library
- Microfrontends Project Library
 - ProjectFeature Service
 - Project Service
 - ProjectConversion Service
- Microfrontends Phase Library
 - PhaseFeature Service
 - PhaseMonitor Service
 - Phase Service
 - PhaseConversion Service

Shell & Micro-frontends

- Each micro-frontend is served on a different url.
- Module federation
 - Library sharing (webpack.config.js)
 - Micro-frontend loading (routing module)

Applications Interaction Example

Exercise

Environment Setup

- Install Shell (VPN or Remote Access required)
 - git clone <https://redacted.address/module-federation/shell.git>
 - git checkout workshop
 - npm i
- Install project-info (VPN or Remote Access required)
 - git clone <https://redacted.address/module-federation/project-info.git>
 - git checkout workshop
 - npm i

Exercise

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/redacted.address/view?usp=sharing>

Discussion

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